

Analysis of Bioactive Chemical Compounds of *Trogoderma granarium* (Insecta: Coleoptera: Dermestidae) Using Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

Methanolic extract of bioactive compounds of *Trogoderma granarium* was assayed. GC-MS analysis of *Trogoderma granarium* revealed the existence of the Pentanoic acid, 1,1-dimethylpropyl ester, (1H)-Pyrimidinone, 5-chloro-4,6-diphenyl, Cyclobutanemethanol, α -methyl-, Nitro-2-methyl-1,3-propanediol, Hydroxylamine, O-(2-methylpropyl)-, Uridine, 2',3'-O-(phenylmethylene)-, Acetic acid, 2-benzoylthio-, 2-oxo-2-phenylethyl ester, methylpropyl-, Uridine, 2',3'-O-(phenylmethylene)-, 5'-(4-methylbenzenesulfo, Indolinol, 1-benzoyl-, Benzeneethanol, β -methyl-, (s)-, Acetic acid, 2-benzoylthio-, 2-oxo-2-phenylethyl ester, Phenacyl thiocyanate, Deoxy-L-ribose-2,5-dibenzoate, Methenamine, Alanine, N-methyl-n-propargyloxycarbonyl-, decyl ester, Benzoyl chloride, Thiophene-2-ol, benzoate, Ethanone, -(5-nitrotetrazol-2-yl)-1-phenyl-, 2,5-Dimethylhexane-2,5-dihydroperoxide, Benzamide, N-(3-benzylthio-1,2,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-, Methyl p-(2-phenyl-1-benzimidazolyl)benzoate, Methyl-2-phenoxyethylamine, Pentaborane(11), cis-Methoxy-5-trans-methyl-1R-cyclohexanol, Nitro-1-phenyl-3-(tetrahydropyran-2-yloxy)propan-1-one, cis-Methoxy-5-trans-methyl-1R-cyclohexanol. *Trogoderma granarium* produce many important secondary metabolites with high biological activities.

Keyword: gas chromatography – mass spectrometry, bioactive chemical compounds, *Trogoderma granarium*.

INTRODUCTION

The khapra beetle, *Trogoderma granarium* Everts, is one of the world's most feared stored-product pests. In fact, it has been described as one of the 100 worst invasive species worldwide^{1,2}. *Trogoderma granarium* is a serious pest of stored products under hot dry conditions. Reproduction may be so rapid that larvae are found in large numbers in the surface layers of binned grain. Its discovery in a non-infested area usually leads to an immediate quarantine of suspected goods and an expensive eradication and control effort³⁻⁹. *T. granarium* contaminates non-host cargo and packing. The insect also infests spices, dried gums, seeds, dried fruits and other dried proteinaceous plant materials. The Khapra beetle occurs in very low numbers and can survive for a long period as an inactive state. Larvae feed on a wide variety of stored products and dried foods¹⁰⁻¹⁹. They prefer whole grain and cereal products such as wheat, barley, and rice, but larvae have been recorded on the following: oats, rye, corn, dried blood, dried milk, fishmeal, ground nuts, flour, bran, malt, flax seed, alfalfa seed, tomato seed, pinto beans, black-eyed cowpeas, sorghum seed, grain straw, alfalfa hay, noodles, cottonseed meal, dried fruits, lima beans, coconuts, garbanzos, lentils, powdered yeast, and many others. Because of its refuge seeking behavior, it is extremely difficult to eradicate this insect from premises or transport facilities, and the existence of a special type of recurrent dormancy in the

larval stage enables populations to exploit times of food abundance and to survive long periods of deprivation²⁰⁻²⁵. In addition, this pest appears relatively tolerant to insecticides and many fumigants especially at larval stage and has been steadily increasing its geographic range during the last century²⁶. Established infestations are difficult to control because of the beetle's ability to live without food for long periods of time and to survive on foods of low moisture content. These beetles tend to crawl into tiny cracks and crevices and remain there for long periods, making them relatively tolerant to many surface insecticides and fumigants²⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laboratory culture

Larvae (3 mm length) of *T. granarium* were obtained from same-age rearing. Insects were fed with soft wheat flour and beer yeast (95:5) and incubated in darkness at a constant temperature of 30°C and a relative humidity of 70%. Parent adults were provided by the college of science for woman university of Babylon²⁸⁻³³. The extraction was performed by adding 100 ml methanol to the whole body insect powder. Methanol was used as solvent control.

Gas chromatography – mass spectrum analysis

The GC-MS analysis of the *Trogoderma granarium* extract was made in a (Agilent 789 A) instrument under

Decane
Rt=3.247
Mw=142.172151

Pentanoic acid dimethylpropyl ester, 1,1-
Rt=3.356
MW=172.14633

2(1H)-Pyrimidinone chloro-4,6-diphenyl-, 5-
Rt=3.636
MW=282.05599

Cyclobutanemethanol, alpha-methyl-
Rt=3.739
MW=100.088815

2-Nitro-2-methyl-1,3-propanediol
Rt=3.813
MW=135.053158

Hydroxylamine methylpropyl-, O-(2-
Rt=4.311
MW=89.084064

Uridine (phenylmethylene)-methylbenzenesulfo, 2',3'-O 5'-(4-
Rt=5.582
MW=486.109686

2-Indolinol, 1-benzoyl-
Rt=5.725
MW=239.094628

Benzeneethanol, beta-methyl-, (s)-
Rt=6.045
MW=136.088815

Acetic acid 2-benzoylthio-, 2-oxo-2-phenylethyl ester
Rt=6.159
MW=314.06128

Phenacyl thiocyanate
Rt=6.514
MW=177.024835

3-Deoxy-L-ribose-2,5-dibenzoate
Rt=6.571
MW=342.110338

Methenamine
Rt=6.755
MW=140.106196

2,2-Diethyl-N-ethylpiperidine
Rt=6.743
MW=169.18305

Alanine, N-methyl-n-propargyloxycarbonyl-, decyl ester
Rt=6.852
MW=325.22531

Benzoyl chloride
Rt=6.995
Mw=140.0028925

Thiophene-2-ol, benzoate
Rt=7.264
MW=204.024501

Ethanone, -(5-nitrotetrazol-2-yl)-1-phenyl-
Rt=7.767
MW=233.054889

Phenacyl thiocyanate
Rt=8.082
MW=177.024835

2,5-Dimethylhexane-2,5-dihydroperoxide
Rt=8.174
MW=178.120509

Benzamide, N-(3-benzylthio-1,2,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-
Rt=8.511
MW=327.050005

Methyl p-(2-phenyl-1-benzimidazolyl)benzoate
Rt=8.700
MW=328.121178

1-Methyl-2-phenoxyethylamine
Rt=9.123
MW=151.099714

Pentaborane(11)
Rt=9.066
MW=66.132602

3-cis-Methoxy-5-trans-methyl-1R-cyclohexanol
Rt=9.015
MW=144.115029

2-Nitro-1-phenyl-3-(tetrahydropyran-2-yloxy)propan-1-one
Rt=9.392
MW=279.110672

1-(1,4-cyclohexadienyl)-2-methylaminopropane
Rt=9.638
MW=151.1361

1-Phenyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)-diazene oxide
Rt=10.520
MW=212.094963

1- Isobutyraldehyde, propylhydrazone
Rt=11.498
MW=128.131349

Acetoxyacetic acid, nonyl ester
Rt=11.727
MW=244.1674595

computer control at 70 eV about 1µL of the methanol extract was injected into the GC-MS using a micro syringe and the scanning was done for 45 minutes. The time from when the injection was made (Initial time) to when elution occurred referred to as the Retention time (RT). Helium gas was used as a carrier as well as an eluent. The flow rate

of helium was set to 1ml per minute³⁴⁻⁷¹. Compounds were identified by comparing their spectra to those of the Wiley and NIST/EPA/NIH mass spectral libraries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gas chromatography and mass spectroscopy analysis of

, 1,1-dimethylpropyl ester , (1H)-Pyrimidinone , 5-chloro-

2-Pentanol , 3-chloro-4-methyl-, (R*,R*)-(+) Rt=11.967 Mw=136.065493	7-Hydroxy-3-(1,1-dimethylprop-2-enyl)coumarin RT=12.425 MW=230.094295	Trans-2,3-Epoxyoctane RT=13.375 MW=13.375 MW=128.120115	Hexadecanoic acid , methyl ester RT=14.628 MW=270.25588	Cyclopentaneundecanoic acid , methyl ester RT=14.908 MW=268.24023
1-(+)-Ascorbic acid 2,6-dihexadecanoate RT=15.263 MW=652.49142	Tridecanoic acid RT=15.389 MW=214.19328	7-Amino-1,3,5-triazaadamantane RT=15.618 MW=154.121846	N-[3,5-Dinitropyridin-2-yl]proline RT=15.698 MW=282.060034	Pterin-6-carboxylic acid RT=15.601 MW=207.039239
Ethyl undecyl carbonate RT=15.864 MW=15.864	Eicosanoic acid ,phenylmethyl ester RT=16.047 MW=402.349781	9-Octadecenoic acid ,(Z)-, methyl ester RT=16.247 MW=296.27153	Methyl stearate RT=16.470 MW=298.28718	3-Chloropropionic acid , tridec-2-ynyl ester RT=16.648 MW=286.169958
9-octadecenoic acid ,2,2,2-trifluoroethyl ester RT=16.745 MW=364.258915	Ketone , 2,2-dimethylcyclohexyl methyl RT=15.973 MW=154.135765	2-Undecene , (Z)- RT=16.087 MW=154.172151	Cis - 13-Octadecenoic acid , methyl ester RT=16.253 MW=296.27153	1,3-Dioxolane , 4-ethyl-5-octyl-2,2-bis(trifluoromethyl)-, cis- RT=17.071 MW=350.168049
i-Propyl 9-tetradecenoate RT=17.512 MW=268.24023	Butyl 9-tetradecenoate RT=17.638 MW=282.25588	Octadecane , 1,1'-[1,3-propanediylbis(oxy)]bis- RT=21.059 MW=580.615833		

Table 1. Bioactive chemical compounds identified in methanolic extract of *Trogoderma granarium*.

compounds was carried out in methanolic extract of *Trogoderma granarium*, shown in Table 1. The GC-MS chromatogram of the peaks of the compounds detected was shown in Figure 1. Chromatogram GC-MS analysis of the methanol extract of *Trogoderma granarium* showed the presence of fifty three major peaks and the components corresponding to the peaks were determined as follows. The First set up peak were determined to be Pentanoic acid

4,6-diphenyl, Cyclobutanemethanol, α -methyl-, Nitro-2-methyl-1,3-propanediol, Hydroxylamine, O-(2-methylpropyl)-, Uridine, 2',3'-O-(phenylmethylene)-, Acetic acid, 2-benzoylthio-, 2-oxo-2-phenylethyl ester, methylpropyl)-, Uridine, 2',3'-O-(phenylmethylene)-, 5'-(4-methylbenzenesulfo, Indolinol, 1-benzoyl-, Benzeneethanol, β -methyl-, (s)-, Acetic acid, 2-benzoylthio-, 2-oxo-2-phenylethyl ester, Phenacyl

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of methanolic leaves extract of *Trogoderma granarium*

thiocyanate , Deoxy-L-ribose-2,5-dibenzoate , Methenamine , Alanine , N-methyl-n-propargyloxycarbonyl-, decyl ester , Benzoyl chloride , Thiophene-2-ol , benzoate , Ethanone , -(5-nitrotetrazol-2-yl)-1-phenyl- , 2,5-Dimethylhexane-2,5-dihydroperoxide , Benzamide , N-(3-benzylthio-1,2,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)- , Methyl p-(2-phenyl-1-benzimidazolyl)benzoate , Methyl-2-phenoxyethylamine , Pentaborane(11) , cis-Methoxy-5-trans-methyl-1R-cyclohexanol , Nitro-1-phenyl-3-(tetrahydropyran-2-yloxy)propan-1-one , cis-Methoxy-5-trans-methyl-1R-cyclohexanol. The Khapra beetle, *Trogoderma granarium* (Coleoptera, Dermestidae) is considered to be one of the most serious pests of stored grain products, various leguminous crops, rice, oat, barley, and rye throughout the world. It is originally occurred in India, and spread to Africa, Europe, South America and East Asia⁷¹. According to FAO estimate, 10 to 25% of the world harvested food is destroyed annually due to insects and rodent pests. Losses caused by *Trogoderma granarium* have been reported to range from 0.2 to 2.9% over a period of 1 to 10.5 months⁷². Chemical insecticides such as malathian, cypermethrin, bifenthrin are used for rapid control, but are expensive, not readily available and may be poisonous to humans and environment. Moreover, malathian and cypermethrin have gone ineffective due to development of resistance in insect pests of stored grain, particularly in *Trogoderma granarium*⁷³⁻⁷⁵.

CONCLUSION

Fifty three bioactive chemical constituents have been identified from methanolic extract of the *Trogoderma granarium* by GC-MS technique.

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